

Uncertainty Propagation for a MPC-Driven Coupled Point Kinetics and Thermal Hydraulics Reactor Model

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ABSTRACT

In this research, a first-order Taylor series approach is adopted to propagate uncertainties in state parameters in a dynamic coupled point kinetics and thermal hydraulics model of a microreactor. Uncertainty propagation is benchmarked against Monte Carlo (MC) sampling for a linearized 13-dimensional state-space reactor kinetics/thermal model driven by a Model Predictive Control (MPC) law. A discrete-time, MPC-aware sensitivity formulation includes sensitivities of 33 input parameters with finite-difference Jacobians. Results show strong consistency between MC and Taylor Series (TS) uncertainty envelopes for major reactor state variables (neutron population, delayed neutron precursor concentrations, etc.), with $\sigma_{MC}/\sigma_{TS} \approx 1.00 \pm 0.01$ after the initial transient. Thermal states exhibit similarly strong agreement. Iodine deviations remain below $\sim 8\%$, while xenon uncertainty ratios peak near ~ 2.0 during the mid-transient before relaxing toward ~ 1.2 – 1.3 . These discrepancies reflect nonlinear I-Xe feedback, the large $\sim 39.9\%$ uncertainty in Xe-135 yield fraction. The study demonstrates that first-order TS propagation provides a computationally efficient and accurate alternative to full MC analysis for near-linear reactor dynamics.

Keywords: Uncertainty Propagation, Taylor Series, Monte Carlo Method, Point Kinetics, Model Predictive Control

1. INTRODUCTION

Uncertainty Propagation (UP) plays a central role in the prediction and safety analysis of nuclear systems. In dynamic reactor simulations—particularly those coupling neutron Point Kinetics Equation (PKE) with Thermal-Hydraulics (TH) feedback—accurate quantification of uncertainties in model parameters is essential for understanding system stability, control response, and safety margins. Such coupled PKE+TH frameworks are widely used to analyze transient behavior, reactivity feedback, and control-system interactions in both conventional and advanced reactor concepts [1, 2, 3].

Previous studies have applied UP and sensitivity analysis to PKE models, demonstrating its importance in reactor dynamics analysis [4, 5, 3]. However, most prior efforts have focused on a small subset of input parameters—such as one of the reactivity coefficients, kinetics data, or thermal feedback constants—thus providing an incomplete picture of the overall uncertainty behavior. In this work, we extend the uncertainty space substantially by including all coefficients for 33 uncertain input parameters spanning both neutron kinetics and TH domains. We propagate these parameter uncertainties using the Taylor Series Method (TSM) and verify the TSM with MC sampling.

The MC method remains the reference standard for nonlinear uncertainty propagation due to its conceptual simplicity and asymptotic accuracy. By repeatedly sampling uncertain input parameters and evaluating model outputs, MC provides a non-parametric benchmark for uncertainty quantification. Its application spans numerous engineering domains including nuclear engineering [6, 7, 8, 9, 4, 5, 10]. However, the computational burden associated with large numbers of model evaluations limits its practicality for online control and high-fidelity transient analyses. In the present work, MC results serve as the reference baseline for assessing the performance of a more computationally efficient TS-based approach.

The TSM represents a classical analytical technique for propagating uncertainties through deterministic models [11]. By linearizing the model response about nominal parameter values, the first-order approximation expresses the output uncertainty in terms of input variances and absolute sensitivity coefficients. Despite neglecting higher-order terms, the TSM often provides sufficiently accurate estimates when input uncertainties are small or locally linear. Beyond nuclear applications, the method has been employed in disciplines such as fluid dynamics [12], soil carbon modeling [13], and life-cycle assessment [14]. In nuclear engineering, TSM has been applied to various codes that have been used to assess uncertainties in unprotected loss-of-flow analyses in sodium-cooled fast reactors [15], nuclear criticality safety analysis [16], and nuclear data uncertainty propagation [17]. Nevertheless, to the authors' knowledge, the application of a TS-based uncertainty propagation framework to the coupled PKE+TH equations—particularly under MPC—has not been reported in the literature.

To address this gap, this paper presents a discrete-time, MPC-aware uncertainty propagation framework based on the first-order Taylor expansion of the coupled reactor kinetics and TH equations. The approach is implemented for a microreactor test case with 33 uncertain parameters and verified with MC sampling. The methodology adheres to the principles outlined in the *Guide to the Expression of Uncertainty in Measurement (GUM)* by the International Organization for Standardization [18].

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1. Background: Holos-Quad Microreactor State-Space Model with MPC

Holos-Quad is a TRISO-fueled, helium-cooled microreactor rated at approximately 22 MW_{th} [19]. Recent work has explored autonomy for such systems using MPC implemented within coupled PKE and lumped TH models [2].

This work builds on reference [2]'s framework by employing a linearized, discrete-time state-space representation of the Holos-Quad dynamics under closed-loop MPC feedback. The augmented state vector includes neutron population, six delayed neutron precursor groups, fuel, moderator, and coolant temperatures, as well as fission-product (iodine and xenon) concentrations and reactivity components, yielding a 13-dimensional state vector. The control input corresponds to the normalized Control Drum (CD) reactivity insertion rate, while system output includes the reactor power. The discrete-time system matrices (A_e, B_e, C_e) are obtained through time-domain linearization and zero-order hold discretization about the nominal steady state. This linearized MPC-aware model provides a computationally efficient testbed for assessing uncertainty propagation methods under realistic control feedback conditions.

2.2. First-Order TS UP

The governing equations, detailed derivation of the state-space model, and the underlying MPC implementation is documented in [2]. For MPC, prediction horizon $N_p = 10$, control horizon $N_c = 4$, sampling time $\Delta t = 0.1$, cost function structure and weights $Q = I$ and $R = 0$, regularization parameter $\lambda = 0$ and control drum velocity is 1.0deg/s. Further details are omitted here for brevity. In our work, we begin from the coupled PKE and TH model under MPC represented in discrete augmented state-space form as,

$$\mathbf{x}_e[k+1] = A_e(\boldsymbol{\theta}) \mathbf{x}_e[k] + B_e(\boldsymbol{\theta}) \Delta \mathbf{u}[k], \quad (1)$$

$$\mathbf{y}[k] = C_e \mathbf{x}_e[k], \quad (2)$$

In the above discrete-time state-space representation, $\mathbf{x}_e[k] \in \mathbb{R}^{n_x}$ denotes the augmented state vector at discrete time index k , which contains the reactor power, delayed neutron precursor concentrations, thermal-hydraulic state variables (e.g., fuel, moderator, and coolant temperatures), iodine and xenon concentration as well as CD reactivity. The vector $\mathbf{y}[k] \in \mathbb{R}^{n_y}$ represents the measurable outputs of the system, normalized reactor power in this case. The matrix $A_e(\boldsymbol{\theta}) \in \mathbb{R}^{n_x \times n_x}$ is the augmented state-transition matrix that captures the ordinary differential equations of the coupled PKE and TH dynamics.

These are written in terms of the uncertain parameters θ which represent uncertainty in the coefficients in these equations. The matrix $B_e(\theta) \in \mathbb{R}^{n_x \times n_u}$ is the input matrix that maps the control input increment $\Delta \mathbf{u}[k]$ (e.g., CD velocity) to changes in the system states (e.g., CD reactivity). The output matrix $C_e \in \mathbb{R}^{n_y \times n_x}$ selects the relevant state variables that are measurable outputs. The discrete-time index k corresponds to a physical time $t_k = k \Delta t$, where Δt is the sampling or integration time step used in the numerical simulation or control implementation. The details of the uncertain parameters, $\theta \in \mathbb{R}^m$, are described in Section 2.4. The nominal values, standard deviations and Probability Distribution Functions (PDFs) of the uncertain parameters are also given in Table I of reference [5]. The matrices $A_e(\theta)$ and $B_e(\theta)$ depend on these parameters through both reactor physics and feedback coupling.

Let $S_k = \partial x_e[k] / \partial \theta \in \mathbb{R}^{n_x \times m}$ denote the state absolute sensitivity matrix. Linearizing the system about nominal parameters gives the recursive relation for propagating the uncertainties.

$$S_{k+1} = A_e S_k + F_k + B_e \frac{\partial(\Delta \mathbf{u}_k)}{\partial \theta}, \quad (3)$$

where

$$F_k = [f_{k,1} \quad f_{k,2} \quad \cdots \quad f_{k,m}], \quad f_{k,i} = \frac{\partial A_e}{\partial \theta_i} x_k + \frac{\partial B_e}{\partial \theta_i} \Delta \mathbf{u}_k. \quad (4)$$

The MPC control law is obtained from the regularized least-squares optimization as detailed in Section 4.1 of [2].

$$\Delta \mathbf{U} = K_{ls} (r - F_x x_k), \quad K_{ls} = (\Phi^T \Phi + \lambda I)^{-1} \Phi^T, \quad (5)$$

where Φ is the dynamic prediction matrix, λ is the regularization parameter, F_x is the stacked state-transition operator, and r is the reference trajectory. The matrix K_{ls} denotes the regularized least-squares gain that maps the predicted output tracking error $(r - F_x x_k)$ to the control increment $\Delta \mathbf{U}$. Selecting the first control increment with $E = [1 \ 0 \ \cdots \ 0]$ gives

$$\Delta \mathbf{u}_k = E \Delta \mathbf{U}. \quad (6)$$

For a prediction horizon length N_p , MPC predicts the future state variables. Linear horizon prediction, \mathbf{Y} , is given as [2],

$$\mathbf{Y} = F_x(\theta) x_k + \Phi \Delta \mathbf{U}, \quad (7)$$

$$\text{where, } F_x = \begin{bmatrix} C_e A_e^1 \\ C_e A_e^2 \\ \vdots \\ C_e A_e^{N_p} \end{bmatrix} \text{ and } \Phi = \begin{bmatrix} CB & 0 & 0 & \cdots & 0 \\ CAB & CB & 0 & \cdots & 0 \\ CA^2B & CAB & CB & \cdots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ CA^{N_p-1}B & CA^{N_p-2}B & CA^{N_p-3}B & \cdots & CA^{N_p-N_c}B \end{bmatrix}. \quad (8)$$

The matrix F_x , often called the *free response matrix*, maps the effect of the current state $\mathbf{x}(k_i)$ on the predicted outputs across N_p . It encodes how the system would evolve in open-loop if no future control increments were applied.

The matrix Φ , often called the *dynamic matrix*, captures the influence of the future control moves $\Delta \mathbf{U}$ on the predicted outputs. Each block row of Φ represents how a control move at time $k_i, k_i + 1, \dots$ propagates through the system dynamics to affect future outputs. Together, F and Φ allow the MPC optimizer to balance the effect of the current state and the future control inputs when minimizing the cost function.

Differentiating with respect to θ and grouping terms, we obtain

$$\frac{\partial \Delta \mathbf{u}_k}{\partial \theta} = K_x S_k - L(H x_k), \quad K_x = -E K_{ls} F_x, \quad L = E K_{ls}, \quad (9)$$

where H collects the parameter derivatives of $F_x(\boldsymbol{\theta})$, i.e., H_i is the differentiation of F_x w.r.t. θ_i

$$H = [H_1 \quad H_2 \quad \cdots \quad H_m], \quad H_i = C_e \frac{\partial A_e^{1:N_p}}{\partial \theta_i}.$$

Substituting Eq. (9) into Eq. (3), the full recursive sensitivity propagation becomes

$$\boxed{S_{k+1} = A_e S_k + F_k + B_e(K_x S_k - L(H \mathbf{x}_k))}, \quad (10)$$

which compactly expresses how parameter uncertainties propagate through the closed-loop, discretized reactor dynamics.

For simplicity we assume the parameter uncertainties are independent of each other, so the covariance matrix of $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ is diagonal,

$$\Sigma_\theta = \text{diag}(\sigma_{\theta_1}^2, \dots, \sigma_{\theta_m}^2),$$

and the corresponding first-order state uncertainty is obtained as

$$\sigma_{\mathbf{x},k} = \sqrt{\text{diag}(S_k \Sigma_\theta S_k^\top)}. \quad (11)$$

This simplifying assumption does not limit the applicability of the theory or the results, as correlated parameter uncertainties can be accommodated by using a full covariance matrix Σ_θ in the same formulation. The present analysis focuses on the independent case for simplicity, while incorporating parameter covariances is an area of future work.

2.3. UP with MC Method

For validation of the TS approach, UP was independently performed using a MC sampling method. Each uncertain model parameter θ_i was sampled from its prescribed PDFs, assuming statistical independence across parameters. A total of N_s random parameter vectors $\{\boldsymbol{\theta}^{(j)}\}_{j=1}^{N_s}$ were drawn, and for each realization, the closed-loop reactor model governed by

$$\mathbf{x}_e^{(j)}[k+1] = A_e(\boldsymbol{\theta}^{(j)}) \mathbf{x}_e^{(j)}[k] + B_e(\boldsymbol{\theta}^{(j)}) \Delta \mathbf{u}^{(j)}[k] \quad (12)$$

was simulated over the entire transient.

The ensemble mean, $\bar{\mathbf{x}}_e[k]$, and standard deviation, $\sigma_{\mathbf{x},k}$, of each state variable were then computed from the results.

Convergence of the MC statistics was monitored using the relative change in the mean and standard deviation between consecutive sample batches until

$$\max \left(\frac{|\bar{\mathbf{x}}_e^{(n)} - \bar{\mathbf{x}}_e^{(n-1)}|}{|\bar{\mathbf{x}}_e^{(n-1)}| + \epsilon}, \frac{|\sigma_{\mathbf{x}}^{(n)} - \sigma_{\mathbf{x}}^{(n-1)}|}{|\sigma_{\mathbf{x}}^{(n-1)}| + \epsilon} \right) < \tau,$$

with a tolerance $\tau = 0.02$. This procedure was repeated for $N_s = 5000$ samples to ensure convergence of the mean and one-sigma uncertainty envelopes.

2.4. Uncertain Input Parameters

The coupled PKE+TH model contains a total of 33 uncertain input parameters, denoted collectively as the vector $\boldsymbol{\theta} \in \mathbb{R}^{33}$. These parameters include the delayed neutron fractions and decay constants (β_i, λ_i), the neutron generation time (Λ), reactivity feedback coefficients ($\alpha_f, \alpha_m, \alpha_c$), the initial power and neutron population (P_0, n_0), the nominal heat deposition fraction (q), the heat capacities for the fuel, moderator, and coolant (C_f, C_m, C_c), the inter-region heat transfer coefficients (K_{fm}, K_{mc}), the coolant

mass flow rate (\dot{M}), and nuclear data quantities such as the microscopic cross section (σ_x), neutron speed (v), fission yields (γ_i, γ_x), and iodine and xenon decay constants (λ_i and λ_x), initial Xenon concentration (X_0) and macroscopic fission cross section (Σ_f). The nominal values and the PDFs were reviewed and listed in [5]. Nuclear data uncertainties (e.g., fission yields, decay constants, \bar{v} , and cross sections) were taken from evaluated ENDF/B libraries and associated covariance data, [20] while engineering measurement uncertainties for power and coolant mass flow rate were bounded using licensing and instrumentation references [21]. The present study is methodological in nature; correlated parameter uncertainties can be incorporated directly through a full covariance matrix Σ_θ , which is planned for future extensions. The initial uncertainties of the state parameters were assumed to be zero.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results demonstrate strong consistency between the MC and TS UP methods across nearly all reactor state variables. Both analyses were performed on the linearized state-space representation of the reactor dynamics, which minimizes nonlinear distortion and explains the close agreement in uncertainty magnitude and temporal evolution. In Fig. 1, the reference trajectory represents a closed-loop load-following maneuver under MPC control, where the control drum reactivity tracks a prescribed normalized power demand subject to actuator constraints. Fig. 1 also shows the time evolution of the MC and TS mean trajectories with their one-sigma envelopes, together with the instantaneous ratio σ_{MC}/σ_{TS} . All state variables are expressed in deviation form about steady-state equilibrium; thus, zero corresponds to nominal operation, with positive and negative values representing deviations above and below steady-state conditions, respectively. After the initial 100 s, the agreement between MC and TS remains within a few percent for the neutron population and all precursor groups, with $\sigma_{MC}/\sigma_{TS} \approx 1.0$ throughout the transient. For the thermal-hydraulic states (fuel, moderator, and coolant temperatures), the uncertainty ratio remains within approximately 2–4% during active transients and gradually settles near unity under quasi-steady conditions. Minor early-time discrepancies arise from the zero initial covariance assumption in the TSM formulation.

The largest deviations occur in the xenon concentration state. The xenon uncertainty ratio peaks near 2.0 during the power maneuver and gradually decreases toward ~ 1.4 – 1.5 at later times, indicating moderate underprediction by the first-order Taylor approximation during feedback-dominated periods. This behavior is attributed to the nonlinear coupling between xenon buildup, neutron flux, and reactivity feedback. Because the TS approach assumes constant linear sensitivities, it cannot fully capture the cumulative nonlinear feedback effects that arise during xenon transient evolution.

The control drum reactivity deviation exhibits a peak uncertainty ratio of approximately 1.05 during active control motion before converging back toward unity. This comparatively small deviation indicates that, although actuator constraints introduce mild nonlinearities, their impact on uncertainty propagation remains limited under the present operating scenario.

Overall, the excellent agreement between MC and TS confirms that, when applied to a linearized dynamic model, the first-order Taylor approach provides an accurate and computationally efficient alternative to full MC uncertainty propagation. For feedback-sensitive states such as xenon, the discrepancy reaches a factor of 2 - exceeding higher than 20% and more under-representation of MC computed uncertainty - demonstrating the qualitative threshold where the TS model fails. However, the TSM demonstrates a substantial computational advantage over the MC approach. Both simulations were performed on the same high-performance computing node equipped with two Intel Xeon Platinum 8160 CPUs at 2.10 GHz. While the MC method required 37601.4 seconds, the TSM completed in 11.19 seconds, corresponding to a speedup of approximately $3360\times$.

State Parameters: MC/Taylor Means $\pm 1\sigma$ and σ Ratio ($t \geq 100$ s)

Figure 1. Time evolution of MC and TS mean trajectories with one-sigma uncertainty bands and the instantaneous ratio σ_{MC}/σ_{TS} for all reactor state variables.

4. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

This work compared MC and TS uncertainty propagation applied to a linearized dynamic model of the Holos-quad microreactor system. The results demonstrate strong agreement between the two methods across nearly all reactor states, with σ_{MC}/σ_{TS} remaining within a few percent of unity for neutron, precursor, and thermal-hydraulic variables. The Taylor approach achieved a computational speedup of approximately $3360\times$ relative to MC, while maintaining high fidelity in uncertainty magnitude and temporal evolution. The largest discrepancy was observed in the xenon concentration state, where the uncertainty ratio peaked near 2.0 during feedback-dominated periods before settling toward ~ 1.4 – 1.5 . Control drum reactivity exhibited only minor deviation (peak ratio ~ 1.05), indicating limited impact of actuator nonlinearities under the present operating conditions. These differences reflect the influence of nonlinear isotope feedback and control dynamics that are not fully captured by first-order linear covariance propagation.

Overall, the results confirm that first-order Taylor-based uncertainty propagation provides an accurate and highly efficient alternative to full MC simulation for closed-loop microreactor load-following analysis within the linear operating regime.

Future work will focus on incorporating adaptive or piecewise linearization strategies to better capture nonlinear feedback effects, systematically integrating full parameter covariance matrices, and extending the framework toward online uncertainty-aware control.

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